

Full-Wave Quasi-TEM Characteristic Impedance of an Imperfectly-Conducting Strip Transmission Line

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Abstract—The quasi-TEM characteristic impedance of an imperfectly-conducting strip transmission line based on a full-wave analysis is investigated. The effect of the imperfect outer conductors of the stripline are accommodated via a dyadic Green's function satisfying surface impedance boundary conditions. The imperfect center conductor is accommodated through the use of a resistive sheet boundary condition and leads to an EFIE formulation for the quasi-TEM strip current. This center strip current subsequently allows computation of the quasi-TEM characteristic impedance. The effect that finite conductivity has on the quasi-TEM characteristic impedance is investigated. The importance of these results for use in future applications is discussed.

Keywords—Stripline; quasi-TEM characteristic impedance; Green's function; imperfect conductors; electric field integral equation; impedance boundary condition; guided wave theory.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stripline field applicators are frequently employed in electromagnetic material characterization measurements [1] and for integrated circuit applications [2]-[3] due to their inherent broadband nature, planar geometry and shielding properties. It is generally assumed that the stripline has perfectly-conducting metallic boundaries and is operated in its principal transverse electromagnetic (TEM) mode. However, in high-temperature material characterization measurements, for example, these wave-guiding boundaries are usually poorly conducting due to the nature of the metal alloys used in fabrication. Fields, which would be confined within a perfectly-conducting stripline structure, can now penetrate into the imperfectly-conducting regions. This causes a shift in the ideal TEM-mode propagation constant and characteristic impedance and consequently can lead to significant errors in the material characterization process. A complex-valued correction to the principal mode propagation constant has been examined, for example, using a variational [4] and full-wave [5] analysis, however, the shift in characteristic impedance has not been thoroughly explored.

The goal of this paper is to provide a rigorous formulation for computing the quasi-TEM characteristic impedance Z_0 of an imperfectly-conducting stripline using a spectral-domain full-wave analysis. This objective is accomplished using the following procedure. First, the electric-field dyadic Green's

function for a general three-dimensional (3D) current source immersed in an imperfectly-conducting parallel-plate background environment having height $2t$ is found with the aid of Hertz potential impedance boundary conditions. Next, the stripline structure is realized by specializing the 3D current to a 2D current flowing in an imperfectly-conducting center strip having infinite length along the guiding axis (z -axis) and width $2w$. Enforcement of a resistive boundary condition [6] on the center strip in the axial Fourier-transform domain leads to an electric field integral equation (EFIE) that is subsequently solved using a non-Galerkin's method of moments (MoM) technique involving Chebyshev polynomials of the first and second kind. Solution of the EFIE leads to the discrete-mode propagation spectrum and natural mode currents for the lossy stripline. Only the principal mode is investigated here since this is the mode that is relevant to the material characterization process or integrated circuits and provides the methodology for computing the quasi-TEM characteristic impedance. Numerical results are given to demonstrate the effects that ground plane and strip losses have on Z_0 . The importance of these results for use in future applications is also discussed.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Geometry

The cross-sectional geometry of a general 3D electric current source density \vec{J} immersed within an imperfectly-conducting parallel-plate background environment is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Cross sectional view of lossy parallel plate guide.

The imperfect metallic ground plates (located at $y = \pm t$) have surface impedance $Z_g = (1+j)\sqrt{\frac{\omega\mu_0}{2\sigma_g}}$ and are assumed to be infinite in extent along the x and z directions. In the above surface impedance relation, ω is the angular frequency and σ_g is the conductivity of the imperfect metallic ground plates. These plates are also assumed to be non-magnetic with permeability μ_0 . The interior medium between the plates has permittivity ε and permeability μ_0 .

B. Parallel Plate Electric Field Dyadic Green's Function

The electric-field dyadic Green's function $\vec{G}^e(\vec{r}|\vec{r}')$ can be identified using an electric-type Hertz potential $\vec{\pi}$ that satisfies the known [7] wave equation $\nabla^2\vec{\pi} + k^2\vec{\pi} = -\frac{\vec{J}}{j\omega\varepsilon}$. The solution of this wave equation is found using the superposition of a principal wave $\vec{\pi}^p$ emanating from source \vec{J} in unbounded space and waves $\vec{\pi}^r$ that are reflected from the introduction of the imperfectly-conducting boundaries at $y = \pm t$ with the source removed, as depicted in Figure 1. Since this background structure is infinite in extent along the x and z directions, Fourier transformation is prompted on those variables ($x \leftrightarrow \xi$ and $z \leftrightarrow \zeta$), resulting in the following transform domain wave equations (for $\alpha = x, y, z$)

$$\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\pi}_\alpha^p(\bar{\lambda}, y)}{\partial y^2} - p^2 \tilde{\pi}_\alpha^p(\bar{\lambda}, y) = -\frac{\tilde{J}_\alpha(\bar{\lambda}, y)}{j\omega\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\pi}_\alpha^r(\bar{\lambda}, y)}{\partial y^2} - p^2 \tilde{\pi}_\alpha^r(\bar{\lambda}, y) = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $p = \sqrt{\xi^2 + \zeta^2 - k^2}$ with $\text{Re}\{p\} > 0$, $\bar{\lambda} = \hat{x}\xi + \hat{z}\zeta$ and $k = \omega\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu_0}$. The total solution is readily found to be

$$\tilde{\pi}_\alpha(\bar{\lambda}, y) = \int_{y'} \frac{e^{-p|y-y'|}}{2p} \frac{\tilde{J}_\alpha(\bar{\lambda}, y')}{j\omega\varepsilon} dy' + W_\alpha^+ e^{-py} + W_\alpha^- e^{py} \quad (3)$$

where the first term in (3) is the principal wave contribution and the second and third terms are the upgoing and downgoing reflected waves, respectively.

Next, the surface impedance boundary condition [6] $\hat{n} \times \hat{n} \times \vec{E} = -Z_g \hat{n} \times \vec{H}$ is enforced at $y = \pm t$. This boundary condition relation can be written in terms of $\vec{\pi}$, resulting in the following transform domain Hertz potential impedance boundary condition relations [5]

$$\tilde{\pi}_\beta(\pm t) = \mp \frac{1}{\sigma_g Z_g} \frac{\partial \tilde{\pi}_\beta(\pm t)}{\partial y} \quad \dots \beta = x, z \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\pi}_y(\pm t)}{\partial y} = \mp j\omega\varepsilon Z_g \tilde{\pi}_y(\pm t) - j\xi \tilde{\pi}_x(\pm t) - j\zeta \tilde{\pi}_z(\pm t)$$

These relations reduce to an anticipated result [8] if the conductors are perfect ($Z_g \rightarrow 0$ and $\sigma_g Z_g \rightarrow \infty$ as $\sigma_g \rightarrow \infty$). Application of these boundary conditions to (3), followed by inverse Fourier transformation and application of the relation $\vec{E} = (k^2 + \nabla \nabla \cdot) \vec{\pi}$ leads to

$$\vec{E}(\vec{r}) = \int_{V'} \vec{G}^e(\vec{r}|\vec{r}') \cdot \vec{J}(\vec{r}') dV' \quad (5)$$

where \vec{G}^e is the desired electric field dyadic Green's function. The details of this derivation are omitted here for the sake of brevity and can be found in [5]. Since the stripline is infinite in extent along the z axis, the above relation in the ζ domain is written

$$\vec{e}(\vec{\rho}, \zeta) = \int_{S'} \vec{g}^e(\vec{\rho}|\vec{\rho}'; \zeta) \cdot \vec{j}(\vec{\rho}', \zeta) dS' \quad (6)$$

where $\vec{e}, \vec{g}^e, \vec{j}$ are the respective quantities of (5) in the ζ domain.

C. EFIE and MoM Solution

The stripline structure in Figure 2 is realized by specializing the 3D current \vec{j} immersed in the lossy parallel plate background environment to a 2D strip current \vec{k} , namely $\vec{j} = \vec{k} \delta(y)$. The center strip supporting this surface current $\vec{k} = \hat{x}k_x + \hat{z}k_z$ is assumed to be thin compared to wavelength λ (where $k_y = 0$ is assumed) and have sheet resistance $R_s = \frac{1}{\sigma_s d}$, with conductivity σ_s and thickness $d \ll \lambda$.

Figure 2. Cross sectional view of lossy stripline.

Enforcing the transform-domain resistive boundary condition [6] $\hat{n} \times \hat{n} \times \vec{e} = -R_s \vec{k}$ (with $\hat{n} = \hat{y}$) on the center strip leads to the coupled EFIE formulation for unknown surface currents k_x and k_z , namely

$$\int_{-w}^w \left[g_{xx}^e(x|x') k_x(x') + g_{xz}^e(x|x') k_z(x') \right] dx' - R_s k_x(x) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\int_{-w}^w \left[g_{zx}^e(x|x') k_x(x') + g_{zz}^e(x|x') k_z(x') \right] dx' - R_s k_z(x) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Note, the impressed source field on the right hand side of (7) and (8) is zero since only the natural mode current is required to compute the characteristic impedance. In addition, $R_s = 0$ if the center conductor is perfectly conducting, as expected.

The above coupled equations can be solved using the MoM. The first step in the MoM solution is to expand the unknown currents, namely

$$k_\beta(x) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_{\beta n} e_{\beta n}(x) \quad \dots \beta = x, z \quad (9)$$

where $e_{\beta n}(x)$ are known expansion functions (Chebyshev polynomials here, see [7] or [8], for example) and $a_{\beta n}$ are the unknown expansion coefficients, leading to 2 equations and $2N$ unknowns. Applying the testing operator

$$\int_{-w}^w t_{\alpha m}(x) \{ \cdot \} dx \quad \dots m = 1, \dots, N \quad ; \quad \alpha = x, z \quad (10)$$

to equations (7) and (8), respectively, leads to the matrix equation $[A][a] = [0]$, where $[A]$ is a known $2N \times 2N$ matrix, $[a]$ is a $2N$ column vector of the unknown expansion coefficients and $[0]$ is the $2N$ null column vector. The determinant of $[A] = 0$ leads to the non-trivial natural mode propagation spectrum and associated currents.

If the stripline has perfect outer and center conductors and is operating in the TEM mode, a unique voltage and current will exist in the cross-sectional plane, and thus a unique characteristic impedance may be defined (ratio of voltage to current for a single travelling wave). In the imperfectly-conducting case, a TEM mode only exists in an approximate sense due to the existence of a finite longitudinal electric field. So long as $|k_x| \ll |k_z|$, a quasi-TEM characteristic impedance can be defined accordingly, namely

$$Z_0 = \frac{V_0}{I_0} \approx \int_0^t e_y(0, y) dy \div \int_{-w}^w k_z(x) dx \quad (11)$$

Since voltage is assumed to be unique (in an approximate sense for the imperfect conductor case), the path integral for voltage is conveniently chosen to be a straight line from $y = 0$ to $y = h$ along $x = 0$, thus only the y directed electric field is implicated. Note, relation (11) is exact in the perfect conductor case (and k_x is identically zero). The effects of finite conductivity on Z_0 are explored in the next section.

III. RESULTS

The effect of finite conductivity on the quasi-TEM characteristic impedance is discussed here. Note, an initial convergence study was performed and it was found that only approximately five to six (i.e., $N = 5$ to 6) Chebyshev polynomial expansion terms were required to achieve convergence to the fifth decimal place in the calculation of all data presented in this section. The convergence study plots are not provided for the sake of brevity.

First, it is important to demonstrate that the strength of the x -directed surface current density k_x is small compared to the z -directed surface current density k_z . This will allow a quasi-TEM characteristic impedance to be defined in accordance with (11), as previously discussed. As a typical example, consider a stripline structure having nearly perfect outer conductors ($\sigma_g = 1 \times 10^{200} = 1.e200$ S/m) with half-spacing $t = 0.635$ mm, a center conductor of half-width $w = 1.5$ mm with conductivity $\sigma_s = 1 \times 10^5, 1 \times 10^6, 1 \times 10^7$ S/m and an operating frequency of $f = 10$ GHz. Figures 3 and 4 show that, at $x = 0.9w$, $|k_x| \approx 0.0013$ while $|k_z| \approx 0.25$ for the case of $\sigma_s = 1 \times 10^5$ S/m, leading to $|k_x|/|k_z| \approx 0.0065$, which satisfies the quasi-TEM assumption. Note, it is found (but not presented here for sake of brevity) through experience that the quasi-TEM assumption is suitable when $\sigma_s, \sigma_g > 1 \times 10^3$ S/m.

Figure 3. Surface current density profile for k_x .

Figure 4. Surface current density profile for k_z .

Next, a free-space filled stripline having outer conductor half spacing 17.38 mm and center strip half width 25 mm is investigated. The operational frequency is 1 GHz and it is assumed $\sigma_g = \sigma_s$. Figure 5 shows that, for large conductivity values ($\sigma_g = \sigma_s = 1 \times 10^9$ S/m), the characteristic impedance is $50-j0 \Omega$ (note, this stripline is ideal for attaching to 50Ω coaxial cables for various testing scenarios due to matching). It is observed, however, that $\text{Re}\{Z_0\}$ increases to 50.6Ω and $\text{Im}\{Z_0\}$ becomes capacitive with value -0.6Ω as the conductivity values decrease to $\sigma_g = \sigma_s = 1 \times 10^4$ S/m. This is expected from elementary transmission line theory in which

$$Z_0 = \sqrt{\frac{R+j\omega L}{G+j\omega C}} = \sqrt{\frac{L}{C} - j\frac{R}{\omega C}} \quad (12)$$

since dielectric loss $G=0$ in this free-space filled stripline example. The center strip finite conductivity increases ohmic heating losses, and thus, resistance R increases, leading to a capacitive reactive effect on Z_0 , as expected via (12). The outer conductors have impedance $Z_g = (1+j)\sqrt{\frac{\omega\mu_0}{2\sigma_g}}$, thus resistance and inductance increase as conductivity σ_g decreases. This leads to an increase in the real part of Z_0 and further negative increase in the imaginary part of Z_0 , in accordance with (12). Thus, the EFIE formulation allows rigorous calculation of Z_0 and also agrees with an anticipated result when compared to elementary transmission line theory.

Figure 5. Quasi-TEM characteristic impedance ($\text{Re}\{Z_0\}$ = solid curve, $\text{Im}\{Z_0\}$ = dashed curve).

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the effect of finite conductivity on the quasi-TEM characteristic impedance of a strip transmission line was explored. A dyadic Green's function was formulated for the imperfectly-conducting parallel-plate background environment satisfying an impedance boundary condition. The stripline structure was realized via an EFIE formulation using a resistive boundary condition on the center strip and solved using the MoM, leading to the natural mode spectrum and associated currents. The characteristic impedance was subsequently investigated using a rigorous full-wave quasi-TEM analysis. It was demonstrated that the transverse surface currents are small compared to the longitudinal surface currents, which justified the use of the quasi-TEM analysis. It was shown that imperfect conductors increase the resistance and capacitive reactance of the characteristic impedance, in agreement with elementary transmission line theory. This analysis is important for future applications in material characterization measurements in which characteristic impedance is a vital quantity [1]. Future research will investigate the combined effects of imperfect conductors and material loading on the quasi-TEM characteristic impedance, leading to improved high-temperature material characterization accuracy.

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